

How Should Character Education Be?

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Editors Group:

Concessionaire: Tsisana Kharabadze

Niyaz Bokvadze

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Author(s) Name and Surname: Dr. Clinical Psychologist Melis Avcı (0009-0009-2241-8049)

Department: Clinical Psychology

University: St Clements University

Title: Dr. Clinical Psychologist

Date: December 2023

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THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX. ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX (ASI) EUROPEAN SCIENCE EVALUATION CENTER KIRCHSTRASSE 4.56761 | RHINELAND-PALATINATE, GERMANY PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 PHONE: +49(177) 8684-353 EMAILS: ASI@EUROPE.DE

Abstract

The inclusion of character as a topic in education is a logical outcome of the fundamental purpose of education, which is to nurture individuals. The aspiration to cultivate wise, accomplished, and esteemed individuals in any society leads us to prioritize character education in children. Families are considered the primary implementers of character education programs, followed by teachers and social life. These programs have been widely acknowledged for their effectiveness in shaping children's character development. At the kindergarten and primary school level, teachers and families play a crucial role in serving as role models and instilling universally accepted values in the younger generation. Regardless of the technique and tactic used, the crucial aspect of character education is in the instructor and the family effectively demonstrating their own principles, integrity, and moral value system as an example of outstanding adult behavior. Character education, rooted in 21st century education skills, emphasizes the

importance of self-awareness, effective communication, and the ability to adapt to one's physical surroundings in accordance with personal needs (cognitive/affective, psychosocial). Consequently, it is evident that character education is intricately connected to the cultivation of various character traits. To summarize, character education programs that incorporate fundamental principles such as exemplary parental role models, a positive school environment, moral growth, fairness in peer relationships, and effective communication have a direct impact on instilling character traits such as responsibility, empathy, collaboration, effective communication, sharing, and cooperation in children and young individuals. Consequently, these programs equip them with essential skills for 21st-century education and cultivate individuals who contribute meaningfully to society and the global community.

Key Words: Character, Human and Character, Character Education, Human and Education, Characterization

Introduction

Throughout history, a significant challenge that has preoccupied humanity is the difficulty to generate a human prototype with the appropriate attributes. The root cause of the issues that occur is the failure of individuals to attain the necessary values, resulting in the loss or ineffectiveness of these values.

Consequently, due to these circumstances, individuals lack mutual respect, rendering it difficult for love to thrive in such an environment. Individuals lack consideration and fail to demonstrate empathy towards one another. The growing prevalence of individuals exhibiting these adverse

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traits leads to emotional desensitization, resulting in a multitude of issues. This scenario hinders the formation of a cohesive community by impeding interpersonal contact among individuals. This societal issue has a profound impact on individuals, leading to detrimental psychological repercussions and a sense of isolation. Nevertheless, the experience of empathy and compassion among individuals, along with harmonious coexistence in an atmosphere characterized by respect and love, serves as a potent antidote to feelings of isolation. These valued attributes are imparted to people in a manner that aligns with their moral growth. The allocation of desirable values to persons is a crucial factor in fostering the moral development of humans. An individual's moral character is shaped by their interactions with the culture they are raised in, and their behaviors are a reflection of this process. Consequently, it can be said that for an individual to possess the necessary character, they have a significant role within society as part of the educational collective, starting with the family, followed by the school and its many institutions.

To provide a definition for character, we may describe it as "the conduct that arises when an individual embraces the ethical principles and behavioral norms of their society and applies them to their own actions. "The number is 14. Character is formed as a consequence of a certain aspect of one's personality. This trait demonstrates coherence in behavior, as well as accuracy and uninterrupted flow of motions. Personality, when considered in its whole, encompasses character. Thus, it encompasses all the metaphysical and corporeal attributes of the individual. In our current society, character is mostly used to convey moral attributes. Character development starts throughout infancy. The formation of value judgments is made possible via social events within the culture in which it occurs. Seventeen To put it simply, the character of a well-trained and educated individual may be defined as the resolute and unwavering commitment of their soul to adhere to deeply ingrained ideals and values. Eighteen For instance, refraining from making deceptive assertions, displaying generosity, exhibiting benevolence and mercy, as well as abstaining from being generous, deceitful, Behaviors that are morally oriented, such as lying, may be categorized as either negative or good patterns within the character dimension of personality. Within the social context, the acquisition and ongoing development of the character dimension of one's personality takes place. Personality and character characteristics are shaped by the attitudes and actions shown in interpersonal relationships, as well as the resulting outcomes. These character characteristics include being trustworthy and credible, possessing a sense of justice, fearlessness,

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and a strong commitment to respect and dignity. Hence, religious and moral characteristics have significant importance in this particular environment.

What is Character Education?

Character education refers to the education that is not provided at initial stages of life with the aim of improving individuals' moral and ethical qualities in the future (Hoge, 2002). Kamaruddin (2012) argues that character education should include more than only teaching moral values but should also focus on ensuring that individuals possess and demonstrate proper actions. Lickona (1997) describes character development as the deliberate process of helping individuals develop a conscious understanding of values.

The character education method, while known by several names throughout history, was formally introduced in America in the 1860s (Sırrı and Mehmedoğlu, 2015: 125). During the period from the late 1880s to the early 1900s, education primarily emphasized moral values and aimed to instill ethical principles in individuals, with a particular emphasis on aligning these values with one's actions. During these ages, it is highlighted that the moral attributes that were attempted to be instilled were not just the duty of educational institutions such as schools, but also included the whole society. Nevertheless, during the 1920s and 1930s, there were unfavorable notions regarding character education. Even as late as 1940, John Dewey expressed the view that the emphasis should be on democracy and citizenship education rather than character education when imparting moral values to individuals. This viewpoint inevitably resulted in a decline in the character education process. An event has occurred. In response to the environmental degradation throughout the 1950s, the character education provided in schools underwent restructuring to assist young people in resolving their issues. While character education in schools experienced a decline approximately ten years after the mentioned date, it resurfaced in the subsequent decade as a means of promoting values and moral development, as advocated by Kohlberg. The years of the 1980s and 1990s witnessed renewed efforts to foster positive character traits. The objective of character education is to foster a positive outcome. The 1990s saw a surge in character education, which has since become a common feature in educational institutions. (Acat and Aslan, 2011: 9-10; Turan, 2014: 80-81). Thomas Lickona introduced the concept of character education and implemented it within

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a specific framework in the United States. According to the statement, under this system, the school and the teacher have significant obligations in imparting the fundamental principles of morality. Similarly, the realities that shape one's character have been disclosed, along with the necessary measures to foster comprehension of these truths inside educational institutions. The source cited is Kaymakcan and Meydan (2014), page 186. Lickona (1993) argued that in order to restore the disrupted family order caused by the rising prevalence of crime in society, and to enable individuals to thrive in this negative social environment, it is necessary to cultivate a positive character. To successfully achieve the goal during this orientation, it is crucial to generate a sufficient number of ideas on effectively portraying character. Additionally, it is important to engage in thorough reasoning that encompasses the emotional, intellectual, and behavioral aspects of morality. Furthermore, he emphasized the need of educational institutions providing assistance to students in acquiring proficiency in fundamental principles. He asserted that several domains, including the family, society, and educational institutions, have significant obligations in cultivating individuals who possess a comprehensive understanding of ethical conduct. (Ekşi, 2003: 79). Consequently, it is accurate to assert that the school is not solely accountable for the favorable resolution of this scenario. Similar to all other aspects of life, the environment in which we reside also has significant responsibilities (Lickona, 1992, as quoted in Akbaş, 2008: 18). Within this particular methodology, educators must possess proficiency in executing 7 sequential stages in order to effectively impart knowledge pertaining to character. The competences may be enumerated as follows (Ryan and Bohlin, 1999, as referenced in Demirel, 2009: 38-39): 1. Teachers have a professional obligation to prioritize and embrace the aims of learners in their process of character building. 2. Instructors should exemplify excellent character traits in order to serve as role models for others. 3. Instructors should possess the ability to clearly articulate their viewpoints on various ethical matters, while refraining from imposing their own beliefs upon pupils. 4. Educators should possess the capacity to engage in dialogues with their pupils on ethical matters in life. 5. Instructors should cultivate a classroom atmosphere characterized by respect and foster a community where individuals with strong moral principles coexist within the value system. 6. Instructors should instruct students in the art of empathy, fostering their comprehension of other individuals' experiences, and encouraging them to transcend their own perspectives. Teachers should possess the ability to design activities that foster the development of self-sacrificing and ethical conduct in pupils, both within educational institutions and society at large. To ensure the

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provision of effective character education, a set of 11 principles has been established and is presented below. Character education that produces desired results (Demirel, 2009: 38; Kesgin, 2015: 123): 1. Explores the notion of "Character" including emotions, ideas, and conduct. 2. Its objective is to enhance ethical principles with the purpose of cultivating a virtuous character. 3. It fosters a school community that upholds and honors human values. 4. The strategy used is characterized by its effectiveness in including a wide range of information, being pre-established, and having a focus on the future. 5. The program incorporates an academic curriculum that instills respect in all students, fosters character growth, and aids in their overall success. 6. It offers learners chances for moral engagement. One hundred and seventy Education focused on developing character and instilling values. 7. It denotes school staff members who adhere to the same set of principles and are entrusted with the present duty of imparting character education and guiding the students' learning. 8. Its objective is to enhance learners' motivation. 9. Acknowledges the significance of the individuals in his immediate surroundings, such as his family and the people in his environment, in shaping his character, and actively involves them in this developmental process. 10. The character education approach sustains its assistance over an extended duration by fostering shared ethical guidance. 11. The study analyzes the nature of the school, the obligations of school authorities as character instructors, and the degree to which pupils exhibit favorable character traits.

"Character education refers to a form of education that focuses on instilling moral understanding and promoting positive behaviors in students. It aims to cultivate individuals who prioritize moral values in their educational journey." (TDK, <http://www.tdk.gov. en>) Mere knowledge of one's current or future values is insufficient for an individual. The true worth is in attentively considering the stated principles, understanding them, assessing them internally, and incorporating them into one's own life. Currently, character education has a significant and esteemed place. The reference "Ay, 2014: 222" indicates a source citation in the year 2014, with the page number 222.

Upon analyzing the events, ideas, emotions, and pictures associated with character education, it becomes evident that the efficacy of various forms of character education is substantiated via diverse metrics. Character education encompasses various aspects, including academic motivation, goals, competence, commitment to the educational institution, pro-environmental

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behavior, moral judgment, problem-solving skills, self-sufficiency, respect, proficiency in social issues, and trust in the teacher.

Furthermore, character education has the tendency to mitigate several unfavorable circumstances. The following issues include lack of further education, disciplinary measures such as school suspension, anxiety related to courses and subsequent academic failures, drug abuse, and pregnancy. (Brooks and Kaan, 1993; Cassell, 1995; Hogan, 1996; quoted in: Was, Woltz, and Drew, 2006: 150).

Time and attentiveness are crucial factors in cultivating individuals with exemplary character. Character formation, a crucial aspect of personality development, can only be achieved via the process of learning. Personality encompasses all the inherent and acquired traits that differentiate an individual from others, including both internal and external features. Personality undergoes continuous development from infancy till death. Consequently, it is influenced by both indoor and outdoor stimuli. Character, the fundamental pillar of personality, refers to an individual's inherent structural traits that differentiate them from others. The development of personality is mostly influenced by the social environment and family dynamics. The child's development is influenced by the models he observes and the instruction he gets, which are acquired via his experiences in school and home.

CHARACTER EDUCATION AT HOME

Nurturing well-behaved and virtuous children takes dedication and attentiveness. Parents' behavior and the consistent maintenance of such conduct are crucial for children to develop fundamental life skills. The youngster becomes perplexed and exhibits inconsistency due to the careless and haphazard attitudes and approaches. If a youngster does not get the same response to a conduct at a different time, they may experience feelings of frustration, unhappiness, and worthlessness. Being a steadfast and unwavering executor of decisions made with affection is crucial. It is irrelevant what role you hold, or which rule your child disobeys. Regardless of the perceived significance of the situation, it is always preferable to enforce your decisions rather than disregard your child's obstinate and defiant behavior. Every individual in the vicinity of our children has the

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ability to serve as a role model, whether positively or negatively. It is imperative that we recognize the impact these individuals have on our children and actively engage in open communication with them. Additionally, we should strive to reduce the influence of external forces and create situations that promote positive values. It takes time to guide the inherent traits of youngsters towards positive behavior and to instill fundamental ideals in them. Priority should be assigned to responsibility, honesty, respect, and discipline. Subsequently, patience, fairness, leadership, and other qualities should be given precedence. The child's character development would benefit from acquiring these attributes.

"The Power of Language in Character Education"

Assurance

If you need your youngster to possess self-assurance, ask them, "How did you perform?"

Continue to perform well. "It is a significant advancement."

"Indeed, I concur with your viewpoint." "I experience great satisfaction when we engage in collaboration with you."

"You exhibit a high level of caution."

"Highly innovative."

"You are making progress in the correct direction." Thank you for your diligence.

Duty

To instill a sense of responsibility in your kid, express gratitude when they fulfill their commitments by saying "Thank you for honoring your word."

"You are now responsible for this task (purchasing the newspaper, etc.)." I am certain that you will fulfill your obligations with great competence.

"You are accountable for this." I can provide you with a conceptual overview of your task. By doing your schoolwork for you, I will hinder your ability to acquire knowledge.

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Upon completion of your tasks, you are permitted to engage in leisure activities such as watching television and using the internet.

Self-esteem

If you need your youngster to possess elevated self-esteem, express to them: "I genuinely adore you, despite the fact that your academic performance is subpar."

"You possess exceptional talent." Rest certain, there is no one more adept at this task than yourself.

"You possess immense value and uniqueness."

"Currently, I do not harbor anger towards you, but rather towards your conduct."

Internal discipline refers to the practice of self-control and adherence to rules and regulations inside an organization or individual. It involves the ability to regulate one's behavior, maintain focus, and follow established protocols.</p></div>

If you want to instill discipline in your kid, you may consider expressing your disapproval of their conduct by stating, "I found this behavior unfavorable." What other course of action would be more advantageous for you to pursue? "It is commendable that you adhere to punctuality when returning home." Expressing gratitude.

"We discussed the regulations pertaining to your living quarters." "You must complete the necessary tasks before you are allowed to use the computer."

"You deactivated the television without receiving prior instruction to do so." "I observe that you possess a strong resolve regarding this matter."

"You completed your homework without mentioning it. You deserve to have ice cream."

Guidance

If you want your kid to become a leader, you must demonstrate exemplary conduct that serves as a positive influence for others.

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"I was highly satisfied with your unwavering resolve."

"This concluded precisely as anticipated." "You executed the decisions you made with remarkable composure."

"The speech was exceptionally well-delivered." "You made a significant impression on everyone."

"I request that you initiate this game."

"The decision of our destination is up to you."

Frequently repeat the phrases. It will become evident that he is seeking employment.

CHARACTER EDUCATION IN SCHOOL

Character, as an element of one's personality, is developed via the process of acquiring knowledge and skills. Furthermore, it undergoes its crucial development phase beginning from these months of education and extending till puberty. Throughout this process, via the imparted education, the kid may acquire the ability to assume responsibility, articulate their emotions, cultivate self-awareness, foster self-assurance, demonstrate respect for oneself and others, exhibit leadership qualities, provide assistance, and uphold fairness. The initiation of character education may be seen as endeavors to enhance the growth and well-being of the individual and the establishment of human rights and obligations that are essential in a democratic society.

The school environment plays a crucial role in facilitating the child's acquisition of fundamental life skills. Character education in children throughout the pre-school years (up to age 7) is shaped by parental views within the home, the child's observations and imitation, and the social environment. Starting with the child's first day of school, this progression continues as they become more engaged in their home, school, and social surroundings, with the aim of fostering favorable modifications in their conduct or maintaining their current behavior. Character education and intellectual learning should not be seen as distinct domains. Their connection is characterized

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by robust and nurturing support. When a kid is surrounded by a classroom and school atmosphere characterized by mutual respect and affection from both peers and instructors, they will be motivated to exert more effort and achieve success. Consequently, when the student achieves success in his academic pursuits, he will have an increased sense of worth and admiration from his peers. Integrating values into the curriculum, guided by academic knowledge, will enhance students' character education throughout their educational journey and transform them into persons armed with essential life skills. During the months dedicated to teaching the concept of responsibility, various activities were conducted by different teachers. The Turkish teacher tasked students with identifying the components of a sentence related to responsibility. The art teacher instructed students to create a drawing on the topic. The music teacher had students sing a song about responsibility. In the life sciences lesson, students were taught about their responsibilities towards their bodies. Lastly, the mathematics lesson focused on the responsibility of using materials or money. Through the resolution of subject-related challenges, students acquire the invaluable attribute of responsibility.

Teachers have a crucial role in assisting pupils in cultivating and enhancing their characteristics. This is because school-age kids tend to see their instructors as role models rather than their parents. The citation for Yavuzer's work in 2000 may be found on page 168. Regarding this matter, educators should openly impart sound moral frameworks to students, while being cognizant of their role as the primary exemplar inside educational establishments (Bakioğlu and Sılay, 2013, 22). When teachers impart character characteristics to learners, it is important to do so seamlessly and within a structured framework. This may be achieved by providing numerous examples and fostering a genuine appreciation for these qualities. The citation is from Durmuş (2011) on page 125. Within the context of character education, teachers should exhibit specific behaviors to effectively accomplish the desired goal. Firstly, teachers must recognize that fostering student growth is a crucial aspect of their professional duties and should approach their role with a sense of mindfulness. Teachers should be aware that they serve as significant exemplars for their pupils. It is important for them to exhibit exemplary character since they will serve as a model for others in their character development. Teachers should provide speeches in the classroom to impart moral guidance and delineate the distinction between good and evil in life. Moreover, it is essential for teachers to ensure the inclusion of all pupils in these dialogues. Teachers should use their freedom

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of expression during moral lectures without being too dictatorial in their delivery of personal beliefs. As students, it is important to minimize any self-imposed pressure. Teachers should prioritize emphasizing that demonstrating respect for all individuals is the fundamental cornerstone of proper conduct within educational settings. Respect and love should be fundamental in educational institutions. Teachers should facilitate their pupils' comprehension of others' emotions and cultivate a sense of empathy within them. Teachers should facilitate the development of ethical character in pupils by their actions both inside and outside the classroom. (Ryan and Bohlin, 1999, Akt, Ekşi, and Katılım, 2011, pages 127-128). Character education is a persistent and ongoing process; hence instructors have significant obligations and must exhibit more willingness and determination. Furthermore, it is essential that instructors possess the necessary credentials to provide character education (Akkiprik, 2007, 21). Given the aforementioned points, it is crucial to examine a few concepts throughout this training in order to enable instructors to be efficacious and make resolute progress towards the objective. Adhering to these principles is beneficial in terms of attaining favorable outcomes as a consequence of the program. In the United States, character education has been systematically conducted for many years. During this time, some concepts have formed based on the experiences of influential figures in the field of education. The citation for this source is Kanger, 2012, page 58. Lickona (1991, 68-70) outlines the possibility of expressing these ideas in the following manner. 1- Foster a sensitive classroom environment: Students should cultivate personal connections, demonstrate respect and mutual regard, and ensure that each individual feels valued and understands their role within the group. 2- Fulfill the role of a nurturing moral guide and exemplar: Demonstrate exemplary behavior characterized by respect and affection towards learners, promote positive social conduct, ensure equitable treatment of all students, foster inclusivity in classroom discussions, and address disruptive behavior appropriately. 3- Establish an inclusive educational environment: All individuals have the opportunity to instruct the class. In order to ascertain the value of a particular topic of study, it is essential to foster collaboration among all individuals, urging them to actively contribute and assuming shared responsibility. 4- Establish moral discipline: By arousing moral awareness in individuals, foster the growth of individuals who voluntarily adhere to regulations and possess the ability to innovate. Implement the cooperative learning approach in the classroom: This approach allows for collaborative effort among students, while emphasizing the need of acknowledging and appreciating the achievements of others. 6- Imbue kids with values via the curriculum: Utilize

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classes with substantial substance, such as science, literature, and history, as a means to impart significance to values. 7- Foster ethical reasoning: Promote ethical reasoning and deliberate decision-making via the practice of journal writing, interpretation of written texts, engaging in discussions, and doing research. 8- Enable comprehension of learners' conscientious states: Students should be encouraged to assume academic responsibilities by cultivating the practice of acknowledging and celebrating their present work within the learning environment. 9- Promote natural learning in the classroom, particularly within the school setting: Utilize role models to facilitate the many phases of natural learning. Employ individuals who possess the necessary abilities and qualifications. 10- Teach methods of dispute resolution: This instruction assists learners in developing ethical abilities to handle conflicts fairly and without exerting coercion on the other party. 11- Establish a moral culture that fosters positive development within the educational institution: Under the guidance of the school principal, enforce discipline throughout the school, involving all members of the school. Cultivate an environment that prioritizes values, allowing for the formation of a student council that is grounded in reality and facilitates discussions among adults about moral situations that reinforce the values being taught in the classroom. Teachers who have important responsibilities in character education must adhere to general principles. Additionally, educators should ensure that the learning environment adequately supports the character development of both the teacher and the students. Antes and Nardini (1994), who performed ethical research in this area, outlined the necessary measures to guarantee that both instructors and learners had a democratic character. 1- By integrating the teaching process with the practical aspects of students' lives, they might be provided with the chance to contemplate their own experiences and ideas. 2- Activities may be devised where students can collaboratively assume each other's responsibilities. During intergenerational events, students from older age groups will develop the virtue of patience towards their peers and serve as role models while providing assistance. This leads to a favorable augmentation in interpersonal connections. 3- Learners have the ability to establish a setting where they may express their thoughts on school life and choose the most suitable form of communication for interacting with diverse individuals. It provides tangible chances for moral teaching that are not part of the curriculum. 31 4- They have the ability to assist pupils in engaging in philanthropic endeavors that facilitate their interaction with their surroundings and foster their feeling of accountability. Engaging in an environmental organization or paying a visit to a nursing home might be significant endeavors now. Teachers may

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serve as role models for pupils in the school and classroom setting, guiding them in decision-making processes and promoting their active involvement in decision-making. 6- They may use everyday occurrences that take place inside the classroom or school environment, given that it is an educational institution. For instance, during a conversation about physical altercations or mocking one another on the school premises, students might demonstrate empathy for their peers by being attuned to their emotions and showing consideration. 7- Facilitating students' ability to articulate ideas to diverse audiences and enhance their communication proficiency via fostering critical thinking may effectively contribute to the development of a coherent identity. Writing and reading activities may be used to unveil ethical and moral concepts. 9- Students might initiate conversations by applying the moral situations presented in the educational curriculum to their own experiences. The dilemmas that arise during conflicts, which are often covered in history classes, may be applied to similar circumstances. 10- They may foster the development of personal discipline in learners. Within this particular environment, the position of disciplinary directorship has significant importance. Teachers must exemplify the act of accepting constructive criticism. 11- The educational setting may be organized in a manner that effectively communicates democratic principles, such as collaboration and mutual sharing. This model is exceptional since it effectively imparts and embodies ideals within this particular setting. 12- They have the ability to develop shared educational exercises to enhance the interpersonal communication abilities of students. 13- Attitudes, values, and character qualities may be effectively taught via ethically beneficial role-play, conversation, or creative activities. 14- Family members might be consulted to establish a shared perspective on ethical matters. By comprehending, learners may uncover shared concepts, and eventually, they can provide assistance in this scenario (Akt, Yıldırım, 2007, 86-87). Ekşi (2003, 79-96) asserts that instructors have significant duties to ensure the proper implementation of character education. Teachers should consider the following responsibilities: being mindful of our interactions with students, treating them equitably, approaching them with kindness and respect, avoiding favoritism, addressing negative behavior promptly, and refraining from actions such as ridicule that can harm a student's self-esteem and well-being. Furthermore, it is worth mentioning that the significance of the other person's viewpoints is emphasized by encouraging positive conduct in the learner and reducing their apprehension about making errors. As to Ryan (1992, 287-304), teachers must possess proficiency in seven distinct domains to

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cultivate a favorable character and serve as an exemplary figure in moral education. The following points should be noted:

- 1- *The instructor must recognize their significant responsibility in fostering the student's character and moral development.*
- 2- *The instructor must possess high moral character and actively fulfill the responsibilities associated with their profession.*
- 3- *The instructor needs to provide a clear and explicit explanation of their own perspectives on values and morals.*
- 4- *It should motivate the learner to develop an interest in ethics.*
- 5- *The instructor should possess the capability to establish a conducive ethical environment, a shared space for assistance inside the educational institution.*
- 6- *Teachers should have the capacity to disclose actions inside the educational institution that facilitate the growth of pupils' empathy skills towards others.*
- 7- *Students should be empowered to cultivate their empathy abilities.*

The investigations have shown that bestowing prizes does not provide a favorable impact on individuals' production levels. When an individual, aware of an impending reward for their effort, prioritizes the reward above the actual task at hand, the job itself becomes secondary. Thus far, in over 10 scrutinized investigations, it has been noted that those who were documented to obtain accolades as a consequence of the research often opted for the least demanding duty. In the absence of a reward, circumstances undergo a complete reversal. Upon observation, it becomes evident that when youngsters are not informed about the possibility of receiving rewards, they tend to choose tasks that beyond their capabilities (Kohn, 1994).

Research indicates that the process of moral development typically starts at around 18 months of age. Typically, children begin their schooling at the age of 6 or later. Prior to this, their moral

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development is mostly influenced by their family (Berkowitz and Grych, 2000). During this era, it is crucial for children to focus on observing good and right behaviors, while avoiding exposure to bad influences that may have detrimental effects on their character development. Several prevalent character qualities may be instilled in children throughout early childhood, which encompasses the period from 18 months to 6 years of age. Examples of the aforementioned circumstance include traits such as empathy, sociability, egalitarianism, self-respect, self-control, compassion, tolerance, honesty, and a penchant for innovation. Currently, families have a significant burden of obligation. It is important for families to strive to instill these qualities in their children throughout the specified timeframe, while considering the child's individual stage of development. During this process, it is quite improbable to anticipate that these character states would promptly capture the person's attention. Due to the inherent egocentricity of infants, they persist in prioritizing their own interests to a certain extent. Currently, they sometimes refrain from participating in truthful conduct. These processes are all observable occurrences in the child's development. To summarize, character education, which is intended to be instilled in individuals by their parents, is a kind of long-term investment. The source cited is Berkowitz and Grych (2000). Now, family members have an additional obligation. When attempting to cultivate desirable character characteristics in a kid, families should exhibit patience towards their undesirable conduct, since it is an inherent aspect of a person's growth and maturation.

There are several diverse recommendations about the obligations of people' parents in relation to character education. Berkowitz and Grych (1998), prominent figures in character education, provide five distinct strategies that families might use to facilitate their children's character education. They may be listed as follows.

Explanation: According to Berkowitz and Grych, the primary strategy that families may use to their advantage in education is to leverage the cause-and-effect link when explaining a situation to children. The only aspect that necessitates the family's focus throughout this endeavor is to effectively communicate the reasons behind the incorrectness of the conduct, using a mode of communication that is comprehensible to them. The youngster, upon seeing the impact of his

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actions on another person's feelings, may only come to his own understanding when he becomes aware of the underlying causes of this circumstance.

Without a question, children see us as role models and should observe our exemplary conduct. However, it is as important for them to understand the underlying rationale behind our actions. To effectively teach kids appropriate behaviors, it is crucial to comprehend the underlying reasons behind their actions. To clarify, it is important for us to elucidate the rationale for our action, which is not morally incorrect, and assist others in demonstrating similar behavior (Lickona, 1983).

Anticipation: A significant aspect of character education is that parents have specific desires for their own children. Berkowitz and Grych analyze the key aspects that must be prioritized to achieve favorable outcomes in relation to requests using three distinct approaches. Families should establish robust but attainable objectives for their children, possess an understanding of their children's capabilities, and discern their areas of proficiency and areas of deficiency. If families maintain modest aspirations and desires for their children, the children will similarly limit the ambitions they eventually strive to accomplish. In contrast, those raised by families with lofty expectations that exceed their capabilities may experience feelings of boredom and anger as a result of the burden of obligation. Thus, families compel individuals to have a sense of inadequacy. It is crucial for families who establish objectives for their children and contemplate the milestones they want to attain to effectively communicate these aims and desires to the kid, while also expressing their own ideas on the matter.

In addition to this, families have the additional duty of providing guidance to their children in order to assist them in attaining their objectives.

Maintenance and Support; *If the care needs of the child are met at the right time and as it should be, children will be securely attached to their families and their self-esteem will develop. In this way, individuals' moral reasoning abilities develop at an early age.*

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Democratic Family, Democratic Decision Making and Discussion: There exists a well-recognized assertion that "Rules alone are insufficient to impart moral principles." Berkowitz and Grych argue that this assertion is false and assert that rules, when implemented effectively by instructors, play a crucial role in shaping character and moral development.

Being a Model: To achieve favorable outcomes in character education, those who were raised in families should serve as role models for others.

Results

And someone who has a strong moral compass, demonstrates conscientiousness towards distinguishing between ethical and unethical conduct, acknowledges their obligations, exhibits impartiality in assessing situations, refrains from falsehoods, upholds principles of fairness, and displays empathy by considering the perspectives of others. The cultivation of individuals with specialized skills and their widespread presence within a nation is a societal framework that is aspired to be present in every global locality. Nations have established this as an objective and endeavor to attain it. Character education, now used as a means to accomplish this objective, has reached a noteworthy stage. Character education encompasses a multitude of distinct meanings. The most widely acknowledged definition of this concept refers to the act of imparting universally recognized moral principles and qualities to people. Virtues, in contrast to values, are universal attributes that are universally acknowledged and remain consistent throughout societies and individuals. Characteristics such as wisdom, impartiality, self-control, positive demeanor, loving approach, honesty, gratitude, and humility are examples of the virtues that Thomas Cickon, an influential figure in character education, believes individuals should possess. These are essential traits that an individual must possess to develop a resilient character, regardless of the circumstances of their upbringing. Character education, which focuses on the development of individuals' personalities, operates inside the emotional realm of the individual. Consequently, it takes a significant amount of time to get the intended outcomes. Due to the fact that attaining objectives in this domain requires a longer duration compared to accomplishments in the cognitive and psychomotor domains. Now, families, together with the educational institution and teacher,

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have significant obligations in attaining the intended objectives of this education. Evidence from research corroborates this assertion. When examining character education techniques in the universe, it is evident that more good outcomes are achieved when the family actively participates in this kind of instruction.

To enhance the prominence of character education in our society, it is crucial to incorporate additional information on this subject into educational programs designed for students aged 6-12. This age range is particularly significant as it is when conscience and value traits begin to develop, thus influencing the formation of positive character and fostering the growth of morally upright individuals. This is a crucial aspect that must be considered in order to establish an enduring and environmentally friendly ecosystem.

An interesting observation is that the majority of research undertaken in this sector consistently finds that both family and school have a collaborative role in facilitating the development of resilient and virtuous persons as they transition into adulthood. Currently, there are three distinct scenarios that should serve as the foundation for advancing this collaboration into a more favorable position. They may be listed as follows:

- Initially, schools should endeavor to convey to families the significance of their role in their children's developmental journey. During the demonstration, people may see how the child's academic progress is enhanced by the synergy between the family and the school.
- Certain families may refrain from engaging with the school due to a perceived lack of competence in certain areas. To address this issue, it is necessary to provide environments where families may feel at ease and not see themselves as deficient. These spaces should prioritize not just academic achievement but also provide opportunities for families to express their ideas and perspectives. Another factor contributing to families' reluctance to work with the school is their perception of being unwelcome due to a lack of genuine communication established by the instructors. Educational institutions should have a clear policy for the accommodation of families, and all staff members should adhere to this policy (Berkowitz and Bier, 2005).

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According to Davidson (2004), there are 12 distinct tactics that instructors may use to foster the development of both the moral and performance aspects of the learner's character. The following items may be listed as:

1. Learners are consistently presented with the question "What is the significance of life to you?" in a certain sequence. Pose thought-provoking inquiries that encourage introspection and critical thinking, such as "explore the concept of happiness" or "how can we cultivate a more purposeful existence?"
2. Facilitate the growth of learners' own character by promoting their self-awareness of their unique abilities and qualities that set them apart from others.
3. Assist students in developing tools that they may independently evaluate as they progress towards their defined objectives. Prompt them to assess their development and devise a strategy appropriately.
4. Instruct pupils to establish objectives for their future and articulate the kind of person they want to become. As they go along this trajectory, prompt them to contemplate how they may make judgments in alignment with ethical principles and how they will conduct themselves towards diverse others.
5. Instruct students to acquire knowledge about the historical background of the locations where they received education and the cities in which they reside. Prompt them to contemplate the culture and history of this particular location.
6. Foster students' awareness of certain values in their academic pursuits, elucidate the ethical implications of undesirable occurrences such as cheating and plagiarism, and underscore the detrimental impact they have on their peers' educational experiences.
7. Foster dialogue by soliciting the perspectives of all individuals on ethical principles. Now, ensure that every concept is well supported and that the learners are exposed to each concept.

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8. Foster students' inclination to scrutinize the societal messages disseminated by mass media and the internet based on their own value systems, comprehend the intended meaning behind such messages, and interrogate if they align with our own set of values.
9. Arrange for professionals from other fields to visit the educational institution and engage in conversations with students, focusing on the principles and practices of ethical work. Inquire with these individuals about their behavioral tendencies when faced with a particularly challenging choice.
10. Provide students with exemplars of persons who possess robust personalities, often emphasize their distinctive traits, and encourage critical thinking by posing questions such as "What attributes contribute to their strength?" and "What distinct characteristics are typically found in individuals who create innovations of this nature?"
11. Facilitate students' engagement with the services available in their surroundings. Assist him/her in formulating suggestions on how to enhance the environmental benefits of these services in his/her local community.
12. Educate pupils on doing tasks of high quality by cultivating within them a sense of self-efficacy and fostering self-assurance.

Consequently, a greater number of favorable outcomes are seen when the efforts made at school and at home are mutually reinforcing. The outcomes meet the expectations of both the instructors and the family. This approach facilitates the development of individuals with robust character, unwavering self-assurance, and a profound sense of self-worth.

Limitation

The limitations of the research are limited to the scope of the subject in the light of world literature and data. The research was conducted by limiting closely related authors and literature topics. Restricted to literature review.

Notifications

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Publication ethics of our university's relevant regulations; It is a national-based scientific study that aims to ensure that scientific research and publications are carried out in accordance with basic principles such as honesty, openness, objectivity, respect for the findings and creations of others, and works to achieve this, aiming at these principles in the field of relevant sciences.

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Mehmet Fatih KAYAN

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